
Supplementary Material for the article “METAFO_R: A Hybrid Metaheuristics Framework for Single-Objective Continuous Optimization Problems”

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S1 Introduction

This report contains the supplementary material of the paper “METAFO_R: A Hybrid Metaheuristics Framework for Single-Objective Continuous Optimization Problems”. The report is organized as follows: Section S2 provides links to downloadable materials associated with this article. These materials include PDFs with the original descriptions of the benchmark suites, raw and processed data presented in the article, and the source code of METAFO_R. Section S3 lists all the functions in the $f_{\text{CEC}'05}$, $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$, and f_{SOCO} benchmarks, as well as their main types, properties, and reference optima. Section S4 presents the following: (i) the complete list of METAFO_R parameters, (ii) the list of forbidden configurations when executing METAFO_R as used in `irace`, and (iii) additional parameters used to execute the framework. Finally, Sections S5 and S6 give, respectively, the complete set of boxplots and convergence plots of the 31 compared algorithms on $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ with $d \in \{30, 100\}$, f_{SOCO} with $d \in \{750, 1250\}$ and f_{MIX} with $d \in \{50, 100\}$.

S2 Downloadable material

S2.1 Benchmark functions

The original description of the 50 static benchmark continuous functions belonging to the CEC'05 and CEC'14 “Special Session on Single Objective Real-Parameter Optimization” [3,2] and to the Soft Computing (SOCO'10) “Test Suite on Scalability of Evolutionary Algorithms and other Metaheuristics for Large Scale Continuous Optimization Problems” [1] can be downloaded from:

Benchmark functions: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18401412>

S2.2 Experimental data, scripts and plots

The raw data gathered in our experiments, the processed data used to create the boxplots, ECDFs/AOC plots and convergence plots, the script we used to process the raw data, and full set of plots are available for download here:

Experimental data, scripts and plots: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18362465>

S2.3 METAFO_R source code

The source code of METAFO_R implemented in C/C++ will be made publicly available in the GitHub repository below once the article is published:

S3 Benchmark Functions

Table S1: CEC'05 Benchmark Problems: Properties, Domains, and Biased Optima.

$f_{\#}$	Name	Type	Properties	Domain	Biased Optima
f_1	Shifted Sphere	Unimodal	Separable, shifted	$[-100, 100]^d$	-450
f_2	Shifted Schwefel's 1.2	Unimodal	Non-separable, shifted	$[-100, 100]^d$	-450
f_3	Shifted Rotated High Conditioned Elliptic	Unimodal	Non-separable, rotated, shifted	$[-100, 100]^d$	-450
f_4	Shifted Schwefel's 1.2 + Noise	Unimodal	Non-separable, shifted, noisy	$[-100, 100]^d$	-450
f_5	Schwefel's 2.6 (optimum on bounds)	Unimodal	Non-separable, optimum on bounds	$[-100, 100]^d$	-310
f_6	Shifted Rosenbrock	Multimodal	Non-separable, shifted, narrow valley	$[-100, 100]^d$	390
f_7	Shifted Rotated Griewank (no bounds)	Multimodal	Non-separable, rotated, shifted, no bounds (optimum outside init.)	$[0, 600]^d$	-180
f_8	Shifted Rotated Ackley (optimum on bounds)	Multimodal	Non-separable, rotated, shifted, optimum on bounds	$[-32, 32]^d$	-140
f_9	Shifted Rastrigin	Multimodal	Separable, shifted, many local optima	$[-5, 5]^d$	-330
f_{10}	Shifted Rotated Rastrigin	Multimodal	Non-separable, rotated, shifted, many local optima	$[-5, 5]^d$	-330
f_{11}	Shifted Rotated Weierstrass	Multimodal	Non-separable, rotated, shifted, fractal landscape	$[-0.5, 0.5]^d$	90
f_{12}	Schwefel's 2.13	Multimodal	Non-separable, shifted	$[-\pi, \pi]^d$	-460
f_{13}	Expanded Extended Griewank's + Rosenbrock's (F_8F_2)	Multimodal	Non-separable, expanded	$[-5, 5]^d$	-130
f_{14}	Shifted Rotated Expanded Scaffer's F_6	Multimodal	Non-separable, rotated, shifted, huge number of local optima	$[-100, 100]^d$	-300
f_{15}	Hybrid Composition Function	Hybrid	Non-separable, hybrid composition, mixed properties	$[-5, 5]^d$	120
f_{16}	Rotated Version of Hybrid Composition Function F_{15}	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, mixed properties	$[-5, 5]^d$	120
f_{17}	F_{16} + Noise in Fitness	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, noisy	$[-5, 5]^d$	120
f_{18}	Rotated Hybrid Composition Function	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, optimum on bounds	$[-5, 5]^d$	10
f_{19}	Rotated Hybrid Composition Function (narrow basin)	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, narrow basin	$[-5, 5]^d$	10
f_{20}	Rotated Hybrid Composition Function (optimum on bounds)	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, optimum on bounds	$[-5, 5]^d$	10
f_{21}	Rotated Hybrid Composition Function 3	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, ill-conditioned	$[-5, 5]^d$	360
f_{22}	Rotated Hybrid Composition Function 3 (optimum on bounds)	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, optimum on bounds, ill-conditioned	$[-5, 5]^d$	360
f_{23}	Non-continuous Rotated Hybrid Composition Function	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, non-continuous	$[-5, 5]^d$	360
f_{24}	Rotated Hybrid Composition Function 4	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, optimum on bounds	$[-5, 5]^d$	260
f_{25}	Rotated Hybrid Composition Function 4 (no bounds)	Hybrid	Non-separable, rotated, hybrid composition, optimum on bounds, no bounds (optimum outside init.)	$[2, 5]^d$	260

Table S2: CEC'14 Benchmark Problems: Properties, Domains, and Biased Optima (Functions f_1 – f_{22})

$f_{\#}$	Name	Type	Properties	Domain	Biased Optimum
f_1	Rotated High Conditioned Elliptic Function	Unimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, quadratic ill-conditioned	$[-100, 100]^d$	100
f_2	Rotated Bent Cigar Function	Unimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, narrow ridge structure	$[-100, 100]^d$	200
f_3	Rotated Discus Function	Unimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable	$[-100, 100]^d$	300
f_4	Shifted and Rotated Rosenbrock's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, narrow valley to optimum	$[-100, 100]^d$	400
f_5	Shifted and Rotated Ackley's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable	$[-100, 100]^d$	500
f_6	Shifted and Rotated Weierstrass Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, continuous but non-differentiable on dense set	$[-100, 100]^d$	600
f_7	Shifted and Rotated Griewank's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable	$[-100, 100]^d$	700
f_8	Shifted Rastrigin's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, separable, huge number of local optima	$[-100, 100]^d$	800
f_9	Shifted and Rotated Rastrigin's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, huge number of local optima	$[-100, 100]^d$	900
f_{10}	Shifted Schwefel's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, separable, huge number of local optima; second-best far from optimum	$[-100, 100]^d$	1000
f_{11}	Shifted and Rotated Schwefel's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, huge number of local optima; second-best far from optimum	$[-100, 100]^d$	1100
f_{12}	Shifted and Rotated Katsuura Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, continuous but nowhere differentiable	$[-100, 100]^d$	1200
f_{13}	Shifted and Rotated HappyCat Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable	$[-100, 100]^d$	1300
f_{14}	Shifted and Rotated HGBat Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable	$[-100, 100]^d$	1400
f_{15}	Shifted and Rotated Expanded Griewank's plus Rosenbrock's Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable, expanded composite	$[-100, 100]^d$	1500
f_{16}	Shifted and Rotated Expanded Scaffer's F6 Function	Multimodal	Shifted, rotated, non-separable	$[-100, 100]^d$	1600
f_{17}	Hybrid Function 1 (N=3)	Hybrid	Shifted, rotated, non-separable subcomponents, mixed structure	$[-100, 100]^d$	1700
f_{18}	Hybrid Function 2 (N=3)	Hybrid	Shifted, rotated, non-separable subcomponents, mixed structure	$[-100, 100]^d$	1800
f_{19}	Hybrid Function 3 (N=4)	Hybrid	Shifted, rotated, non-separable subcomponents, mixed structure	$[-100, 100]^d$	1900
f_{20}	Hybrid Function 4 (N=4)	Hybrid	Shifted, rotated, non-separable subcomponents, mixed structure	$[-100, 100]^d$	2000
f_{21}	Hybrid Function 5 (N=5)	Hybrid	Shifted, rotated, non-separable subcomponents, mixed structure	$[-100, 100]^d$	2100
f_{22}	Hybrid Function 6 (N=5)	Hybrid	Shifted, rotated, non-separable subcomponents, mixed structure	$[-100, 100]^d$	2200

Table S3: SOCO'10 Benchmark Problems: Properties, Domains, and Biased Optima.

$f_{\#}$	Name	Type	Properties	Domain	Biased Optimum
f_1	Shifted Sphere	Unimodal	Shifted, separable, easy (dimension-by-dimension)	$[-100, 100]^d$	-450
f_2	Shifted Schwefel 2.21	Unimodal	Shifted, non-separable	$[-100, 100]^d$	-450
f_3	Shifted Rosenbrock	Multimodal	Shifted, non-separable, easy (dimension-by-dimension)	$[-100, 100]^d$	-390
f_4	Shifted Rastrigin	Multimodal	Shifted, separable, easy (dimension-by-dimension), many local optima	$[-5, 5]^d$	-330
f_5	Shifted Griewank	Multimodal	Shifted, non-separable	$[-600, 600]^d$	-180
f_6	Shifted Ackley	Multimodal	Shifted, separable, easy (dimension-by-dimension)	$[-32, 32]^d$	-140
f_7	Shifted Schwefel 2.22	Unimodal	Shifted, separable, easy (dimension-by-dimension)	$[-10, 10]^d$	0
f_8	Shifted Schwefel 1.2	Unimodal	Shifted, non-separable	$[-65.536, 65.536]^d$	0
f_9	Shifted Extended f_{10}	Unimodal	Shifted, non-separable, easy (dimension-by-dimension)	$[-100, 100]^d$	0
f_{10}	Shifted Bohachevsky	Unimodal	Shifted, non-separable	$[-15, 15]^d$	0
f_{11}	Shifted Schaffer	Unimodal	Shifted, non-separable, easy (dimension-by-dimension)	$[-100, 100]^d$	0
f_{12}	Hybrid: NS-F9 with F1	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.25$)	$[-100, 100]^d$	0
f_{13}	Hybrid: NS-F9 with F3	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.25$)	$[-100, 100]^d$	0
f_{14}	Hybrid: NS-F9 with F4	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.25$)	$[-5, 5]^d$	0
f_{15}	Hybrid: NS-F10 with NS-F7	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.25$), shifted	$[-10, 10]^d$	0
f_{16}^*	Hybrid: NS-F9 with F1	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.5$)	$[-100, 100]^d$	0
f_{17}^*	Hybrid: NS-F9 with F3	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.75$)	$[-100, 100]^d$	0
f_{18}^*	Hybrid: NS-F9 with F4	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.75$)	$[-5, 5]^d$	0
f_{19}^*	Hybrid: NS-F10 with NS-F7	Hybrid	Hybrid composition, mixed separability ($m_{ns} = 0.75$), shifted	$[-10, 10]^d$	0

S4 Parameter settings

S4.1 Parameters of METAFO \mathbb{R}

METAFO \mathbb{R} has a total of 104 parameters. However, not all of them are used when the framework is executed. The actual number of parameters depends on the options selected for **PSOmod**, **DEmod**, **CMA-ESmod** and **LSmod** and the algorithm component **Execution**. In Table S4 we show the complete list of parameters of METAFO \mathbb{R} , their type and domain, and the specific condition(s) under which each parameter has to be configured. We show the name of the parameters as defined in the code of METAFO \mathbb{R} (these are the names users have to use as command line arguments when executing the framework) and next to them, in parenthesis, their corresponding names as used in the paper.

We also make the following observations to the information in Table S4

- 1 - In the column **Name**, we indicate the way parameters are used as command line arguments when executing METAFO \mathbb{R} , with the caveat that users have to add "--" before each parameter and a space between the parameter's name and the desired value, e.g., --execProbaType 1.
- 2 - In the column **Type**, we show the type of the parameters of METAFO \mathbb{R} , which can be categorical (indicated with letter "c"), integer (indicated with letter "i"), or real (indicated with letter "r"). We use categorical parameters to represent: (i) alternatives for implementing a component when these alternatives have no inherent order (e.g., component $\text{Pert}_{\text{info}}$, which has the command line name `perturbation1CS`, can be implemented using options 0 = none, 1 = $\text{Pert}_{\text{info}}$ -Gaussian, 2 = $\text{Pert}_{\text{info}}$ -Lévy and 3 = $\text{Pert}_{\text{info}}$ -uniform); (ii) modules that can be enabled or disabled (e.g., **DEmod**, whose command line name is `useDE`, is enabled when `useDE = 1` and disabled when `useDE = 0`); and (iii) the approaches used in a hybrid implementation and the order in which they will be executed, e.g., when **Execution** = EXE-multiple phases, parameter `hybridCombination` can take options such as PD, to indicate that **PSOmod** and **DEmod** are enabled and that **PSOmod** is executed before **DEmod**, or PDC, to indicate that **PSOmod**, **DEmod** and **CMA-ESmod** are enabled and that the execution order is **PSOmod** followed by **DEmod** followed by **CMA-ESmod**, and so on. Also, we use integer and real parameter types for numerical parameters (e.g., `omega1 = 0.55` and `localSearchBgtDivide = 37`).
- 3 - In the column **Values**, we specify the different options with which a component can be implemented or the domain of the numerical parameters. On the one hand, for implementing a algorithm component, users have to indicate the integer corresponding to the option they want to use, e.g., the component DE-Base Vector, whose command line name is `baseVecType`, can take any of the following integer options: 0 = BV-random, 1 = BV-best, 2 = BV-target-to-best, 3 = BV-directed-random and 4 = BV-directed-best. On the other hand, for parameters with numerical values, user have to indicate a value in the given interval, e.g., `stepSize`, which corresponds to parameter β in **DEmod**, can take any real value in the interval $[0, 1]$, and branching, which is required when `topology = Top-hierarchical` is used, can take any integer value in the interval $(2, 20)$.
- 4 - In the column **Conditions**, we give the conditions that, when verified, require the corresponding parameter to be configured. Some parameters, such as **Execution**, **Vector-Basis**, and **localSearch**, do not require any specific conditions; however, most parameters need to be configured only when some other parameters are active in the implementation.

Table S4: List of parameters of METAFO \mathbb{R} , their type, their domain, and the conditions under which they have to be configured.

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
Execution Component			
executionType (Execution)	c	0=EXE-component-based, 1=EXE-probabilistic, 2=EXE-multiple phases	

Table S4 (Continued.)

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
execProbaType	c	0=EXE-PB-uniform, 1=EXE-PB-normal, 2=EXE-PB-levy	executionType = 1
execProbaStd	r	(0.01, 1)	execProbaType \in {1, 2}
hybridCombination	c	{PD, DP, PC, CP, DC, CD, PDC, PCD, DPC, DCP, CPD, CDP}	executionType \in {1, 2}
execBudget1	r	(0.01, 1)	executionType \in {1, 2}
execBudget2	r	(0.01, 1)	executionType \in {1, 2}
execBudget3	r	(0.01, 1)	hybridCombination \in {PDC, PCD, DPC, DCP, CPD, CDP}
General components available for all modules			
reinitialization (Re-initialization)	c	0=none, 1=RI-change, 2=RI-similarity	
vectorBasisType (Vector-Basis)	c	0=VB-natural, 1=VB-eigenvector, 2=VB-eigenvector, 3=VB-eigenvector	useDE = 1, useCMAES = 1, useDE = 1 \wedge useCMAES = 1
ω_2 parameter			
omega2CS (ω_2)	c	0= ω_1 , 3=IW-random, 4=IW-constant	executionType = 0 \wedge hybridCombination \in {PD, DP, PC, CP, PDC, PCD, DPC, DCP, CPD, CDP}
omega2 ($\omega_{2,t=0}$)	r	(0.0, 1.0)	omega2CS = 4
DNPP component			
DNPP	c	0=DNPP-rectangular, 1=DNPP-spherical, 2=operator_q	omega2CS \in {0, 2, 3, 4}
operator_q	c	0=DNPP-standard, 1=DNPP-Gaussian, 2=DNPP-discrete, 3=DNPP-Cauchy-Gaussian	DNPP = 2

Table S4 (Continued.)

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
randNeighbor	c	0=false, 1=true	DNPP = 2
operatorCG_parm_r	r	(0.00, 1.00)	operator_q = 3
topology component			
topology (topology)	c	0=Top-ring, 1=Top-fully-connected, 2=Top-wheel, 3=Top-Von Neumann, 4=Top-random edge, 5=Top-hierarchical, 6=Top-time-varying	$\text{omega2CS} \in \{0, 2, 3, 4\}$
modelOfInfluence (modelOfInfluence)	c	0=Mol-best-of-neighborhood, 1=Mol-fully informed, 2=Mol-ranked fully informed	$\text{omega2CS} \in \{0, 2, 3, 4\}$
tSchedule	i	(2, 10)	topology = 5
branching	i	(2, 20)	topology = 6
Accelerations coefficients component			
accelCoeffCS (AC)	c	0=AC-constant, 1=AC-random, 2=AC-time-varying, 3=AC-extrapolated	$\text{DNPP} \in \{0, 1\} \wedge ((\text{DNPP} = 2) \vee (\text{operator}_q = 0))$
phi1	r	(0.00, 2.50)	accelCoeffCS = 0
phi2	r	(0.00, 2.50)	accelCoeffCS = 0
initialPhi1	r	(0.00, 2.50)	accelCoeffCS $\in \{1, 3\}$
finalPhi1	r	(0.00, 2.50)	accelCoeffCS $\in \{1, 3\}$
initialPhi2	r	(0.00, 2.50)	accelCoeffCS $\in \{1, 3\}$
finalPhi2	r	(0.00, 2.50)	accelCoeffCS $\in \{1, 3\}$
ω_1 parameter			

Table S4 (Continued.)

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
omega1CS (ω_1)	c	0=IW-constant 1=IW-linear decreasing, 2=IW-linear increasing, 3=IW-random, 11=IW-self-regulating, 12=IW-adaptive based on velocity, 13=IW-double exponential self-adaptive, 14=IW-rank-based, 15=IW-success-based, 16=IW-convergence-based	omega2CS \in {0, 2, 3, 4}
omega1 ($\omega_{1,t=0}$)	r	(0.00, 0.99)	omega1CS = 0
initialIW (ω_{1min})	r	(0.00, 0.99)	omega1CS \in {2, 3, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16}
finalIW (ω_{1max})	r	(0.00, 0.99)	omega1CS \in {2, 3, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16}
iwSchedule	i	(1, 10)	omega1CS = 2
iw_par_eta	r	(0.10, 1.00)	omega1CS = 11
iw_par_lambda	r	(0.10, 1.00)	omega1CS = 12
iw_par_alpha_2	r	(0.00, 1.00)	omega1CS = 16
iw_par_beta_2	r	(0.00, 1.00)	omega1CS = 16
"Informed" perturbation component			
perturbation1CS (Pert _{info})	c	0=none, 1=Pert _{info} -Gaussian, 2=Pert _{info} -Lévy, 3=Pert _{info} -uniform	omega2CS \in {0, 2, 3, 4}
magnitude1CS (PM)	c	1=PM-constant value, 2=PM-Euclidean distance, 3=PM-obj.func. distance, 4=PM-success rate	perturbation1CS \in {1, 2, 3}
magnitude1 (PM $_{t=0}$)	r	(0.0, 1.0)	magnitude1CS \in {1, 4}
mag1_par_l_CS	c	0=adaptive, 1=constant	magnitude1CS = 2
mag1_par_l	r	(0.0, 1.0)	mag1_par_l_CS = 1
mag1_par_m	r	(0.0, 1.0)	magnitude1CS = 3
mag1_par_success	i	(1, 50)	magnitude1CS = 4

Table S4 (Continued.)

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
mag1_par_failure	i	(1, 50)	magnitude1CS = 4
Mtx component (U_{1t}^i and U_{2t}^i)			
randomMatrix (Mtx)	c	0=none, 1=Mtx-random diagonal, 2=Mtx-random linear, 3=Mtx-exponential map, 4=Mtx-Euclidean rotation, 5=Mtx-Euclidean rotation _{all} , 6=Mtx-Increasing group-based	DNPP $\in \{0, 1\}$
angleCS (α)	c	0= α -constant, 1= α -Gaussian, 2= α -adaptive	randomMatrix $\in \{3, 4, 5\}$
rotationAngle	i	(0, 40)	angleCS = 0
angleSD	r	(0.01, 40.00)	angleCS = 1
angle_par_alpha	i	(1, 40)	angleCS = 2
angle_par_beta	r	(0.01, 0.90)	angleCS = 2
PSOmod general components			
clampVelocity	c	0=false, 1=true	omega2CS $\in \{0, 2, 3, 4\}$
unstuckVelocity	c	0=false, 1=true	omega2CS $\in \{0, 2, 3, 4\}$
ignorePbest	c	0=false, 1=true	omega2CS $\in \{0, 2, 3, 4\}$
"Random" perturbation component			
perturbation2CS (Pert _{rand})	c	0=none, 1=Pert _{rand} -rectangular, 2=Pert _{rand} -noisy	
magnitude2CS (PM)	c	1=PM-constant value, 2=PM-Euclidean distance, 3=PM-obj.func. distance, 4=PM-success rate	perturbation2CS $\in \{1, 2\}$
magnitude2 (PM _{t=0})	r	(0.0, 1.0)	magnitude2CS $\in \{1, 4\}$

Table S4 (Continued.)

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
mag2_par_1_CS	c	0=adaptive, 1=constant	magnitude2CS = 2
mag2_par_l	r	(0.0, 1.0)	mag2_par_1_CS = 1
mag2_par_m	r	(0.0, 1.0)	magnitude2CS = 3
mag2_par_success	i	(1, 50)	magnitude2CS = 4
mag2_par_failure	i	(1, 50)	magnitude2CS = 4
ω_3 parameter (controls the influence of perturbation2CS)			
omega3CS (ω_3)	c	0= ω_1 , 3=IW-random, 4=IW-constant	perturbation2CS \in {1, 2}
omega3 ($\omega_{3,t=0}$)	r	(0.0, 1.0)	omega3CS = 4
Local search component			
localSearch (LSmod)	c	0=none, 1=CMAES, 2=MTSIs	
localSearchBudget (LS-budget)	r	(0.01, 1)	localSearch \in {1, 2}
localSearchBgtDivide (LS-divide)	i	(1, 100)	localSearch \in {1, 2}
CMA-ESmod components			
useCMAES (CMA-ESmod)	c	0=false, 1=true	
cmaes_MtxType (CMAES-Mtx)	c	-1=CMAES-Mtx-cov-then-diag, 0=CMAES-Mtx-covariance, 1=CMAES-Mtx-diagonal	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1
cmaes_restart (CMAES-restart)	c	0=false, 1=true	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1
cmaes_Weights (CMAES-weights)	c	0=CMAES-weights-linear 1=CMAES-weights-equal 2=CMAES-weights-logarithmic	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1
cmaes_lambda	i	[6, 200]	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1
cmaes_par_a	r	(1.0, 10.0)	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1
cmaes_par_b	r	(1.0, 5.0)	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1

Table S4 (Continued.)

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
cmaes_par_c	r	(0.01, 0.99)	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1
cmaes_par_d	r	(1.0, 4.0)	localSearch = 1 \wedge \vee useCMAES = 1
cmaes_par_e	r	(-20.0, -6.0)	cmaes_restart = 1
cmaes_par_f	r	(-20.0, -6.0)	cmaes_restart = 1
cmaes_par_g	r	(-20.0, -6.0)	cmaes_restart = 1
MTSIs components			
mtsls1_iterbias_choice (MTSLS-bias)	r	(-1.0, 1.0)	localSearch = 2
mtsls1_initstep_rate (MTSLS-init-ss)	r	(0.01, 0.99)	localSearch = 2
mtsls1per_ratedim (MTSLS-iterations)	r	(1.0, 3.0)	localSearch = 2
DEmod components			
useDE (DEmod)	c	0=false, 1=true	
baseVecType (DE-Base Vector)	c	0=BV-random, 1=BV-best, 2=BV-target-to-best, 3=BV-directed-random, 4=BV-directed-best	useDE = 1
pctOfDifferences (DE-vector-differences)	r	(0.0, 0.2)	useDE = 1
recombinationType (DE-Recombination)	c	0=RCB-binomial, 1=RCB-exponential	useDE = 1
crossoverRate (p_a)	r	(0.00, 1.00)	useDE = 1
stepSize (β)	r	(0.00, 1.00)	useDE = 1
recomputeVelCS (DE-Recompute Velocity)	c	0=none, 1=RV-goBack, 2=RV-random, 3=RV-position	useDE = 1
vectorsToApplyTo (DE-Vectors)	c	0=V-positions, 1=V-pbest, 2=V-mixture	useDE = 1
applyPSOonlyOnFail	c	0=false, 1=true	useDE = 1 \vee omega2CS \in {0, 2, 3, 4}

Table S4 (Continued.)

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
population component			
populationCS (population)	c	0=Pop-constant, 1=Pop-time-varying, 2=Pop-incremental	
particles (pop)	i	(2, 500)	populationCS \in {0, 1}
initialPopSize (pop _{t=0})	i	(2, 50)	populationCS \in {1, 2}
finalPopSize (pop _{t=max})	i	(3, 500)	populationCS \in {1, 2}
particlesToAdd	i	(1, 10)	populationCS = 2
popTViterations	i	(1, 100)	populationCS = 1
pIntitType (Initialization)	i	(0, 1)	populationCS \in {1, 2}

In Table S5, we show the list of forbidden configurations used by `irace` when configuring METAFOR, i.e., parameter values or combinations of parameter values that are not allowed to be used. When creating new (candidate) configurations, `irace` evaluates whether the configuration is valid using the forbidden configurations file and automatically discards it if it matches any of the forbidden configurations in the list.

Table S5: List of forbidden configurations checked by `irace` when configuring METAFOR.

Forbidden configurations

$\text{executionType} = 1 \wedge \text{hybridCombination} \in \{\text{PC}, \text{CP}, \text{DC}, \text{CD}, \text{PDC}, \text{PCD}, \text{DPC}, \text{DCP}, \text{CPD}, \text{CDP}\}$
 $\text{initialPopSize} > \text{finalPopSize}$
 $\text{particlesToAdd} > (\text{finalPopSize} - \text{initialPopSize})$
 $(\text{populationCS} = 1) \wedge ((\text{particles} < \text{initialPopSize}) \vee (\text{particles} > \text{finalPopSize}))$
 $(\text{topology} = 6) \wedge (\text{modInfluence} = 2)$
 $(\text{branching} > \text{finalPopSize}) \vee (\text{branching} > \text{particles}) \vee (\text{branching} < \text{initialPopSize})$
 $(\text{randNeighbor} = 1) \wedge \text{modInfluence} \in \{0, 2\}$
 $(\text{DNPP} = 2) \wedge \text{randomMatrix} \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$
 $(\text{accelCoeffCS} = 1) \wedge (\text{initialPhi1} \leq \text{finalPhi1})$
 $(\text{accelCoeffCS} = 1) \wedge (\text{initialPhi2} \geq \text{finalPhi2})$
 $(\text{accelCoeffCS} = 3) \wedge (\text{finalPhi1} \leq \text{initialPhi1})$
 $(\text{accelCoeffCS} = 3) \wedge (\text{finalPhi2} \leq \text{initialPhi2})$
 $\text{initialIW} > \text{finalIW}$
 $\text{unstuckVelocity} = 1 \wedge \text{omega1} = 0.0$
 $\text{useDE} = 1 \wedge (\text{particles} < 10)$
 $\text{useDE} = 1 \wedge (\text{initialPopSize} < 10)$

In addition to the forbidden configurations file used by `irace`, METAFO_R also has an internal verification procedure that checks that the software is executed with a valid set of parameters and stops its execution if there is any violation of the verification rules. The procedure is called `getConfig()` and is implemented in the `config.cpp` file in the source code of METAFO_R. Additional parameters used to execute the framework are listed in Table [S6](#).

Table S6: Additional command-line parameters parsed in `getConfig.cpp` that are not listed in Table [S4](#).

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
Benchmark selection			
competition (<code>--competition</code> <code>--suite</code> <code>--benchmark</code>)	c	0= $f_{\text{CEC}'05}$, 1= $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$, 2= f_{SOCO} , 3= f_{MIX} }	
problem (<code>--problem</code> , <code>--function</code>)	i	$f_{\text{CEC}'05}$: [0,24] $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$: [0,21] f_{SOCO} : [0,18] f_{MIX} : [0,49]	Range depends on competition.
dimensions (<code>--dimensions</code>)	i	[2,5000]	Must be between 2 and 5000 (inclusive).
seed (<code>--seed</code>)	i	> 0	Must be strictly positive
Budget and stopping			
evaluations (<code>--evaluations</code>)	i	$i \geq 0$ or $\{-1,-2,-3\}$	Cheat codes: $-1 \rightarrow 1000 \cdot d$, $-2 \rightarrow 10000 \cdot d$, $-3 \rightarrow 5000 \cdot d$; values < -3 are invalid. If <code>iterations</code> <0: computed as <code>evaluations/populationCS</code> if <code>populationCS</code> >0, else as <code>evaluations/initialPopSize</code> if <code>executionType</code> ==2, otherwise <code>evaluations/particles</code> .
iterations (<code>--iterations</code>)	i	i (use $i < 0$ for automatic)	Must be > 0; otherwise reset to <code>dimensions</code> ×15.
maxTimeSec (<code>--maxTimeSec</code>)	r	> 0	
Robustness and error handling			
RRMset (<code>--RRMset</code>)	i	[1,5]	Must satisfy $1 \leq \text{RRMset} \leq 5$.
bypassEE (<code>--bypassEE</code>)	c	flag	When present, expensive evaluations are allowed; otherwise, an error messages is printed.

Table S6 continued from previous page

Name	Type	Values	Conditions
fixConfig (--fixConfig)	c	flag	When present, common errors involving extra parameters are automatically fixed.
Output and logging			
outputPath (--output-path)	s	path string	path to the folder where results will be stored.
useLogs (--yesLogs, --noLogs)	c	{0,1}	-yesLogs→ 1, -noLogs→ 0.
verbose (--verbose, --quiet)	c	{0,1}	-quiet→ 0; -verbose→ 1 and expects an integer verbosity level stored in levelVerbose.
levelVerbose (--verbose argument)	i	[1, 2]	Only read when --verbose is used. Must satisfy $VERBOSE_LEVEL_QUIET \leq levelVerbose \leq VERBOSE_LEVEL_COMPUTATIONS$; otherwise reset to 1.
Other			
help (--help)	c	flag	Prints usage information and exits.

S5 Distribution of the results obtained by the compared algorithms

S5.1 Boxplots $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$, $d = 30$ Fig. S1: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 30$), CMAES variants. Top-left: CMAES_{25OUT1b}; top-right: CMAES_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S2: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 30$) boxplots for CMAES_{DFT}.

Fig. S3: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 30$), DE-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: DE-CMAES_{25OUT1b}; top-right: DE-CMAES_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: DE-CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: DE-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S4: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 30$), DE variants. Top-left: $DE_{25OUT1b}$; top-right: $DE_{25OUTsb}$; bottom-left: DE_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: DE_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S5: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 30$) boxplots for DE_{DFT} .

Fig. S6: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 30$), MTF variants. Top-left: $MTF_{25OUT1b}$; top-right: $MTF_{25OUTsb}$; bottom-left: MTF_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: MTF_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S7: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 30$), PSO-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: PSO-CMAES_{250UT1b}; top-right: PSO-CMAES_{250UTsb}; bottom-left: PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S8: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 30$), PSO-DE hybrids. Top-left: PSO-DE_{25OUT1b}; top-right: PSO-DE_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: PSO-DE_{LD01b}; bottom-right: PSO-DE_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S9: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 30$), PSO- X_{LD01b} /PSO- X_{LD0sb} family (PSO- X). Top-left: PSO- $X_{250UT1b}$; top-right: PSO- $X_{250UTsb}$; bottom-left: PSO- X_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: PSO- X_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S10: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 30$) boxplots for StdPSO_{DFT}.

S5.2 Boxplots $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$, $d = 100$ Fig. S11: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 100$), CMAES variants. Top-left: CMAES_{25OUT1b}; top-right: CMAES_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S12: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 100$) boxplots for CMAES_{DFT}.

Fig. S13: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 100$), DE-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: DE-CMAES_{250UT1b}; top-right: DE-CMAES_{250UTsb}; bottom-left: DE-CMAES_{LDO1b}; bottom-right: DE-CMAES_{LDOsb}.

Fig. S14: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 100$), DE variants. Top-left: $DE_{250UT1b}$; top-right: $DE_{250UTsb}$; bottom-left: DE_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: DE_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S15: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 100$) boxplots for DE_{DFT} .

Fig. S16: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 100$), MTF variants. Top-left: $MTF_{25OUT1b}$; top-right: $MTF_{25OUTsb}$; bottom-left: MTF_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: MTF_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S17: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 100$), PSO-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: PSO-CMAES_{250UT1b}; top-right: PSO-CMAES_{250UTsb}; bottom-left: PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S18: $f_{CEC'14}$ ($d = 100$), PSO-DE hybrids. Top-left: PSO-DE_{25OUT1b}; top-right: PSO-DE_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: PSO-DE_{LD01b}; bottom-right: PSO-DE_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S19: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 100$), PSO-X variants. Top-left: PSO- $X_{250UT1b}$; top-right: PSO- $X_{250UTsb}$; bottom-left: PSO- X_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: PSO- X_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S20: $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$ ($d = 100$) boxplots for StdPSO_{DFT}.

S5.3 Boxplots f_{SOCO} , $d = 750$ Fig. S21: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$), CMAES variants. Top-left: CMAES_{25OUT1b}; top-right: CMAES_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S22: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$) boxplots for CMAES_{DFT}.

Fig. S23: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$), DE-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: DE-CMAES_{25OUT1b}; top-right: DE-CMAES_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: DE-CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: DE-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S24: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$), DE variants. Top-left: $DE_{25OUT1b}$; top-right: $DE_{25OUTsb}$; bottom-left: DE_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: DE_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S25: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$) boxplots for DE_{DFT} .

Fig. S26: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$), MTF variants. Top-left: MTF_{25OUT1b}; top-right: MTF_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: MTF_{LD01b}; bottom-right: MTF_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S27: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$), PSO-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: PSO-CMAES_{25OUT1b}; top-right: PSO-CMAES_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S28: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$), PSO-DE hybrids. Top-left: PSO-DE_{250UT1b}; top-right: PSO-DE_{250UTsb}; bottom-left: PSO-DE_{LD01b}; bottom-right: PSO-DE_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S29: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$), PSO- X variants. Top-left: PSO- $X_{250UT1b}$; top-right: PSO- $X_{250UTsb}$; bottom-left: PSO- X_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: PSO- X_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S30: f_{SOCO} ($d = 750$) boxplots for StdPSO_{DFT}.

S5.4 Boxplots f_{SOCO} , $d = 1250$ Fig. S31: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$), CMAES variants. Top-left: CMAES_{25OUT1b}; top-right: CMAES_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S32: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$) boxplots for CMAES_{DFT}.

Fig. S33: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$), DE-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: DE-CMAES_{250UT1b}; top-right: DE-CMAES_{250UTsb}; bottom-left: DE-CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: DE-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S34: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$), DE variants. Top-left: DE_{250UT1b}; top-right: DE_{250UTsb}; bottom-left: DE_{LD01b}; bottom-right: DE_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S35: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$) boxplots for DE_{DFT} .

Fig. S36: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$), MTF variants. Top-left: MTF_{25OUT1b}; top-right: MTF_{25OUTsb}; bottom-left: MTF_{LD01b}; bottom-right: MTF_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S37: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$), PSO-CMAES hybrids. Top-left: PSO-CMAES_{250UT1b}; top-right: PSO-CMAES_{250UTsb}; bottom-left: PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}; bottom-right: PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S38: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$), PSO-DE hybrids. Top-left: PSO-DE $_{250UT1b}$; top-right: PSO-DE $_{250UTsb}$; bottom-left: PSO-DE $_{LD01b}$; bottom-right: PSO-DE $_{LD0sb}$.

Fig. S39: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$), PSO-X variants. Top-left: PSO- $X_{250UT1b}$; top-right: PSO- $X_{250UTsb}$; bottom-left: PSO- X_{LD01b} ; bottom-right: PSO- X_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S40: f_{SOCO} ($d = 1250$) boxplots for StdPSO_{DFT}.

S5.5 Boxplots f_{MIX} , $d = 50$

Fig. S41: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), CMAES variants (part 1). Left: CMAES_{250UT1b}; right: CMAES_{250UTsb}.

(a) CMAES_{LD01b}

(b) CMAES_{LD0sb}

Fig. S42: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), CMAES variants (part 2). Left: CMAES_{LD01b}; right: CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S43: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$) boxplots for CMAES_{DFT}.

(a) $DE_{250UT1b}$

(b) $DE_{250UTsb}$

Fig.S44: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), DE variants (part 1). Left: $DE_{250UT1b}$; right: $DE_{250UTsb}$.

Fig. S45: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), DE variants (part 2). Left: DE_{LD01b} ; right: DE_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S46: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$) boxplots for DE_{DFT} .

Fig. S47: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), MTF variants (part 1). Left: $MTF_{250UT1b}$; right: $MTF_{250UTsb}$.

(a) MTF_{LD01b}

(b) MTF_{LD0sb}

Fig.S48: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), MTF variants (part 2). Left: MTF_{LD01b} ; right: MTF_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S49: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), $PSO-CMAES$ hybrid variants (part 1). Left: $PSO-CMAES_{250UT1b}$; right: $PSO-CMAES_{250UTsb}$.

(a) PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}

(b) PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}

Fig. S50: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), PSO-CMAES hybrid variants (part 2). Left: PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}; right: PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig.S51: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), PSO-DE hybrid variants (part 1). Left: $PSO-DE_{25OUT1b}$; right: $PSO-DE_{25OUTsb}$.

(a) PSO-DE_{LD01b}

(b) PSO-DE_{LD0sb}

Fig. S52: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), PSO-DE hybrid variants (part 2). Left: PSO-DE_{LD01b}; right: PSO-DE_{LD0sb}.

(b) PSO- $X_{250UTsb}$ Fig. S53: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), PSO variants (part 1). Left: PSO- $X_{250UT1b}$; right: PSO- $X_{250UTsb}$.

(a) PSO- X_{LD01b}

(b) PSO- X_{LD0sb}

Fig. S54: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$), PSO variants (part 2). Left: PSO- X_{LD01b} ; right: PSO- X_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S55: f_{MIX} ($d = 50$) boxplots for StdPSO_{DFT}.

S5.6 Boxplots f_{MIX} , $d = 100$

Fig. S56: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), CMAES variants (part 1). Left: CMAES_{25OUT1b}; right: CMAES_{25OUTsb}.

(a) CMAES_{LD01b}

(b) CMAES_{LD0sb}

Fig. S57: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), CMAES variants (part 2). Left: CMAES_{LD01b}; right: CMAES_{LD0sb}.

(a) CMAES_{DFT}

Fig. S58: $f_{\text{MIX}} (d = 100)$ boxplots for CMAES_{DFT}.

(a) $DE_{250UT1b}$

(b) $DE_{250UTsb}$

Fig. S59: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), DE variants (part 1). Left: $DE_{250UT1b}$; right: $DE_{250UTsb}$.

Fig. S60: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), DE variants (part 2). Left: DE_{LD01b} ; right: DE_{LD0sb} .

(a) DE_{DFT}

Fig. S61: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$) boxplots for DE_{DFT} .

Fig. S62: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), MTF variants (part 1). Left: $MTF_{25OUT1b}$; right: $MTF_{25OUTsb}$.

(a) MTF_{LD01b}

(b) MTF_{LD0sb}

Fig. S63: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), MTF variants (part 2). Left: MTF_{LD01b} ; right: MTF_{LD0sb} .

Fig. S64: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), $PSO-CMAES$ hybrid variants (part 1). Left: $PSO-CMAES_{250UT1b}$; right: $PSO-CMAES_{250UTsb}$.

(a) PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}

(b) PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}

Fig. S65: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), PSO-CMAES hybrid variants (part 2). Left: PSO-CMAES_{LD01b}; right: PSO-CMAES_{LD0sb}.

Fig. S66: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), PSO-DE hybrid variants (part 1). Left: PSO-DE_{25OUT1b}; right: PSO-DE_{25OUTsb}.

(a) $PSO-DE_{LD01b}$

(b) $PSO-DE_{LD0sb}$

Fig. S67: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), $PSO-DE$ hybrid variants (part 2). Left: $PSO-DE_{LD01b}$; right: $PSO-DE_{LD0sb}$.

Fig. S68: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), PSO variants (part 1). Left: PSO- $X_{25OUT1b}$; right: PSO- $X_{25OUTsb}$.

(a) PSO-X_{LD01b}

(b) PSO-X_{LD0sb}

Fig. S69: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$), PSO variants (part 2). Left: PSO-X_{LD01b} ; right: PSO-X_{LD0sb} .

Fig.S70: f_{MIX} ($d = 100$) boxplots for StdPSO_{DFT}.

S6 Converge plots of the compared algorithms

S6.1 Convergence plots $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$, $d = 30$

Fig.S71: Top: $f_{1(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Rotated High Conditioned Elliptic Function); bottom: $f_{2(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Rotated Bent Cigar Function).

Fig.S72: Top: $f_{3(CEC'14)}$ (Rotated Discus Function); bottom: $f_{4(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Rosenbrock's Function).

Fig. S73: Top: f_5 (CEC'14) (Shifted and Rotated Ackley's Function); bottom: f_6 (CEC'14) (Shifted and Rotated Weierstrass Function).

Fig. S74: Top: $f_{7(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Griewank's Function); bottom: $f_{8(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted Rastrigin's Function).

Fig. S75: Top: $f_{9(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Rastrigin's Function); bottom: $f_{10(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Function).

Fig.S76: Top: $f_{11(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Schwefel's Function); bottom: $f_{12(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Katsuura Function).

Fig.S77: Top: f_{13} (CEC'14) (Shifted and Rotated HappyCat Function); bottom: f_{14} (CEC'14) (Shifted and Rotated HGBat Function).

Fig.S78: Top: $f_{15}(\text{CEC}'14)$ (Shifted and Rotated Expanded Griewank's plus Rosenbrock's Function); bottom: $f_{16}(\text{CEC}'14)$ (Shifted and Rotated Expanded Scaffer's F6 Function).

Fig. S79: Top: $f_{17(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 1 ($N=3$)); bottom: $f_{18(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 2 ($N=3$)).

Fig. S80: Top: $f_{19(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 3 ($N=4$)); bottom: $f_{20(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 4 ($N=4$)).

Fig. S81: Top: $f_{21(CEC'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 5 ($N=5$)); bottom: $f_{22(CEC'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 6 ($N=5$)).

S6.2 Convergence plots $f_{\text{CEC}'14}$, $d = 100$

Fig. S82: Top: $f_{1(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Rotated High Conditioned Elliptic Function); bottom: $f_{2(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Rotated Bent Cigar Function).

Fig. S83: Top: f_3 (CEC'14) (Rotated Discus Function); bottom: f_4 (CEC'14) (Shifted and Rotated Rosenbrock's Function).

Fig. S84: Top: $f_5(\text{CEC}'14)$ (Shifted and Rotated Ackley's Function); bottom: $f_6(\text{CEC}'14)$ (Shifted and Rotated Weierstrass Function).

Fig. S85: Top: $f_{7(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Griewank's Function); bottom: $f_{8(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted Rastrigin's Function).

Fig. S86: Top: $f_{9(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Rastrigin’s Function); bottom: $f_{10(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Shifted Schwefel’s Function).

Fig.S87: Top: $f_{11(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Schwefel's Function); bottom: $f_{12(CEC'14)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Katsuura Function).

Fig.S88: Top: f_{13} (CEC'14) (Shifted and Rotated HappyCat Function); bottom: f_{14} (CEC'14) (Shifted and Rotated HGBat Function).

Fig.S89: Top: $f_{15}(\text{CEC}'14)$ (Shifted and Rotated Expanded Griewank's plus Rosenbrock's Function); bottom: $f_{16}(\text{CEC}'14)$ (Shifted and Rotated Expanded Scaffer's F6 Function).

Fig. S90: Top: $f_{17(CEC'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 1 ($N=3$)); bottom: $f_{18(CEC'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 2 ($N=3$)).

Fig. S91: Top: $f_{19(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 3 ($N=4$)); bottom: $f_{20(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 4 ($N=4$)).

Fig. S92: Top: $f_{21(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 5 ($N=5$)); bottom: $f_{22(\text{CEC}'14)}$ (Hybrid Function 6 ($N=5$)).

S6.3 Convergence plots f_{SOCO} , $d = 750$

Fig. S93: Top: $f_{1(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Sphere Function); bottom: $f_{2(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 2.21).

Fig. S94: Top: $f_{3(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Rosenbrock's Function); bottom: $f_{4(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Rastrigin's Function).

Fig. S95: Top: $f_{5(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Griewank's Function); bottom: $f_{6(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Ackley's Function).

Fig. S96: Top: $f_{7(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 2.22); bottom: $f_{8(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 1.2).

Fig. S97: Top: $f_9(\text{SOCO})$ (Shifted Extended f_{10} Function); bottom: $f_{10}(\text{SOCO})$ (Shifted Bohachevsky's Function).

Fig. S98: Top: $f_{11}(\text{SOCO})$ (Shifted Schaffer's Function); bottom: $f_{12}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_1)).

Fig. S99: Top: $f_{13}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_3)); bottom: $f_{14}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_4)).

Fig. S100: Top: $f_{15}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (f_{10} , f_7)); bottom: $f_{16}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9 , f_1)).

Fig. S101: Top: $f_{17(SOCO)}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_3)); bottom: $f_{18(SOCO)}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_4)).

Fig.S102: Top: $f_{19(\text{SOCO})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_{10} , f_7)).

S6.4 Convergence plots f_{SOCO} , $d = 1250$

Fig. S103: Top: $f_{1(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Sphere Function); bottom: $f_{2(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 2.21).

Fig. S104: Top: $f_{3(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Rosenbrock's Function); bottom: $f_{4(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Rastrigin's Function).

Fig. S105: Top: $f_5(\text{SOCO})$ (Shifted Griewank's Function); bottom: $f_6(\text{SOCO})$ (Shifted Ackley's Function).

Fig.S106: Top: $f_{7(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Schwefel’s Problem 2.22); bottom: $f_{8(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Schwefel’s Problem 1.2).

Fig. S107: Top: $f_{9(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Extended f_{10} Function); bottom: $f_{10(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Bohachevsky's Function).

Fig. S108: Top: $f_{11(\text{SOCO})}$ (Shifted Schaffer's Function); bottom: $f_{12(\text{SOCO})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_1)).

Fig. S109: Top: $f_{13(\text{SOCO})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_3)); bottom: $f_{14(\text{SOCO})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_4)).

Fig. S110: Top: $f_{15}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (f_{10} , f_7)); bottom: $f_{16}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9 , f_1)).

Fig. S111: Top: $f_{17}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_3)); bottom: $f_{18}(\text{SOCO})$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_4)).

Fig.S112: Top: $f_{19(\text{SOCO})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_{10} , f_7)).

S6.5 Convergence plots f_{MIX} , $d = 50$

Fig. S113: Top: $f_{1(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Sphere Function); bottom: $f_{2(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated High Conditioned Elliptic Function).

Fig. S114: Top: $f_{3(MIX)}$ (Rotated Bent Cigar Function); bottom: $f_{4(MIX)}$ (Rotated Discus Function).

Fig. S115: Top: $f_{5(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel’s Problem 2.21); bottom: $f_{6(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel’s Problem 1.2).

Fig. S116: Top: $f_{7(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's 1.2 + Noise); bottom: $f_{8(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 2.22).

Fig. S117: Top: $f_{9(MIX)}$ (Shifted Extended f_{10} Function); bottom: $f_{10(MIX)}$ (Shifted Bohachevsky's Function).

Fig.S118: Top: $f_{11(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schaffer’s Function); bottom: $f_{12(\text{MIX})}$ (Schwefel’s 2.6 (bounds)).

Fig. S119: Top: $f_{13(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Ackley's Function); bottom: $f_{14(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted and Rotated Ackley's Function).

Fig.S120: Top: $f_{15(MIX)}$ (Shifted Rosenbrock’s Function); bottom: $f_{16(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Rosenbrock’s Function).

Fig. S121: Top: $f_{17(MIX)}$ (Shifted Griewank’s Function); bottom: $f_{18(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Griewank’s Function).

Fig. S122: Top: $f_{19(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Rastrigin’s Function); bottom: $f_{20(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted and Rotated Rastrigin’s Function).

Fig. S123: Top: $f_{21(MIX)}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Function); bottom: $f_{22(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Schwefel's Function).

Fig. S124: Top: $f_{23(MIX)}$ (Shifted Rotated Weierstrass); bottom: $f_{24(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Katsuura Function).

Fig. S125: Top: $f_{25(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated HappyCat Function); bottom: $f_{26(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated HGBat Function).

Fig. S126: Top: $f_{27(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_1)); bottom: $f_{28(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_3)).

Fig.S127: Top: $f_{29(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_4)); bottom: $f_{30(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_{10}, f_7)).

Fig.S128: Top: $f_{31(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_1)); bottom: $f_{32(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_3)).

Fig. S129: Top: $f_{33(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_4)); bottom: $f_{34(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_{10}, f_7)).

Fig. S130: Top: $f_{35(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 1 ($N=3$)); bottom: $f_{36(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 2 ($N=3$)).

Fig. S131: Top: $f_{37(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid Function 3 ($N=4$)); bottom: $f_{38(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid Function 4 ($N=4$)).

Fig. S132: Top: $f_{39(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 5 ($N=5$)); bottom: $f_{40(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 6 ($N=5$)).

Fig. S133: Top: $f_{41(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid Composition 1); bottom: $f_{42(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 1).

Fig. S134: Top: $f_{43(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 1 + Noise); bottom: $f_{44(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 2).

Fig. S135: Top: $f_{45(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 2 (narrow basin)); bottom: $f_{46(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 2 (opt on bounds)).

Fig. S136: Top: $f_{47(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 3); bottom: $f_{48(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 3 (ill-conditioned)).

Fig. S137: Top: $f_{49}(\text{MIX})$ (Non-continuous Rotated Hybrid); bottom: $f_{50}(\text{MIX})$ (Rotated Hybrid 4).

S6.6 Convergence plots f_{MIX} , $d = 100$

Fig. S138: Top: $f_{1(MIX)}$ (Shifted Sphere Function); bottom: $f_{2(MIX)}$ (Rotated High Conditioned Elliptic Function).

Fig. S139: Top: $f_{3(MIX)}$ (Rotated Bent Cigar Function); bottom: $f_{4(MIX)}$ (Rotated Discus Function).

Fig. S140: Top: $f_{5(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 2.21); bottom: $f_{6(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 1.2).

Fig. S141: Top: $f_{7(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's 1.2 + Noise); bottom: $f_{8(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schwefel's Problem 2.22).

Fig. S142: Top: $f_{9(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Extended f_{10} Function); bottom: $f_{10(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Bohachevsky's Function).

Fig. S143: Top: $f_{11(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Schaffer’s Function); bottom: $f_{12(\text{MIX})}$ (Schwefel’s 2.6 (bounds)).

Fig. S144: Top: $f_{13(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Ackley's Function); bottom: $f_{14(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted and Rotated Ackley's Function).

Fig.S145: Top: $f_{15}(\text{MIX})$ (Shifted Rosenbrock's Function); bottom: $f_{16}(\text{MIX})$ (Shifted and Rotated Rosenbrock's Function).

Fig.S146: Top: $f_{17(MIX)}$ (Shifted Griewank’s Function); bottom: $f_{18(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Griewank’s Function).

Fig. S147: Top: $f_{19(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted Rastrigin's Function); bottom: $f_{20(\text{MIX})}$ (Shifted and Rotated Rastrigin's Function).

Fig. S148: Top: $f_{21(MIX)}$ (Shifted Schwefel’s Function); bottom: $f_{22(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Schwefel’s Function).

Fig. S149: Top: $f_{23(MIX)}$ (Shifted Rotated Weierstrass); bottom: $f_{24(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated Katsuura Function).

Fig. S150: Top: $f_{25(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated HappyCat Function); bottom: $f_{26(MIX)}$ (Shifted and Rotated HGBat Function).

Fig. S151: Top: $f_{27(MIX)}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_1)); bottom: $f_{28(MIX)}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_3)).

Fig. S152: Top: $f_{29(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_9, f_4)); bottom: $f_{30(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (f_{10}, f_7)).

Fig. S153: Top: $f_{31(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_1)); bottom: $f_{32(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_3)).

Fig. S154: Top: $f_{33(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_9, f_4)); bottom: $f_{34(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid comp. (shifted f_{10}, f_7)).

Fig. S155: Top: $f_{35(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid Function 1 (N=3)); bottom: $f_{36(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid Function 2 (N=3)).

Fig. S156: Top: $f_{37(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 3 ($N=4$)); bottom: $f_{38(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 4 ($N=4$)).

Fig. S157: Top: $f_{39(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 5 (N=5)); bottom: $f_{40(MIX)}$ (Hybrid Function 6 (N=5)).

Fig. S158: Top: $f_{41(\text{MIX})}$ (Hybrid Composition 1); bottom: $f_{42(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 1).

Fig. S159: Top: $f_{43}(\text{MIX})$ (Rotated Hybrid 1 + Noise); bottom: $f_{44}(\text{MIX})$ (Rotated Hybrid 2).

Fig. S160: Top: $f_{45(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 2 (narrow basin)); bottom: $f_{46(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 2 (opt on bounds)).

Fig. S161: Top: $f_{47(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 3); bottom: $f_{48(\text{MIX})}$ (Rotated Hybrid 3 (ill-conditioned)).

Fig. S162: Top: $f_{49}(\text{MIX})$ (Non-continuous Rotated Hybrid); bottom: $f_{50}(\text{MIX})$ (Rotated Hybrid 4).

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